

MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MEDICINE

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ANNOTATION Today, as technologies are developing at a rapid pace, it is natural that this process does not limit the field of medicine. Since modern technologies have become very important in medicine, their study is considered one of the important tasks facing every medical worker. In this article, we look at the most important innovations in medicine that are currently revolutionizing the industry and changing healthcare.

Key words: medicine, modern technologies, disease, development of diseases

АННОТАЦИЯ Сегодня, когда технологии развиваются быстрыми темпами, естественно, что этот процесс не ограничивает сферу медицины. Поскольку современные технологии приобрели большое значение в медицине, их изучение считается одной из важных задач, стоящих перед каждым медицинским работником. В этой статье мы рассмотрим наиболее важные инновации в медицине, которые в настоящее время производят революцию в отрасли и меняют здравоохранение.

Ключевые слова: медицина, современные технологии, болезни, развитие болезней.

Introduction. Due to the increase in the rate of development of science and technology, the terminological system been filled with many new words in the last few decades. The current level of development of science places high demands on the language of scientific communication and, above all, on terminology. Despite the fact that there are many fundamental studies on term theory, a number of problems not been solved. Thus, a certain ideal of the term formed in terminology,

according to which strict requirements were set for terminology, especially in scientific speech.

Medical terminology is a collection of words and phrases used by professionals to define scientific concepts in the field of medicine and health care.

There are three areas of medical terminology:

- Anatomical
- Clinical
- Pharmaceutical.

Modern medicine is going through a period of incredible changes thanks to innovative technologies. These technologies will not only improve diagnostic accuracy and treatment efficiency, but will also change the entire healthcare industry. Along with scientific and technical progress, medicine is also developing. Developers and scientists are creating new medical technologies. With each successful step in this direction, doctors are able to make early diagnosis and treatment. This, of course, helps to prevent possible complications and improve the lives of patients. The World Health Organization's Global Strategy for Digital Health 2020-2025 states, "technology-based healthcare must be accessible to patients." Priority directions include ensuring information security and confidentiality, transparency of data processing and strengthening trust in electronic services.

The World Health Organization believes that technology-based medicine should develop as an organic ecosystem that achieves universal health coverage. According to the organization, less developed countries may face obstacles on the way to digitization. In order to eliminate them, it proposed to develop infrastructure, increase human potential and attract investments. More than 60 billion rubles been allocated for the federal project "Development of the network of national medical research centers and introduction of innovative medical technologies" in Russia from 2019 to 2024. The main directions of innovation:

- Development of nuclear medicine
- Development of personalized treatment regimens

□ Use of telemedicine solutions

1. Artificial intelligence and machine learning

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning have become an integral part of modern medicine. AI algorithms can analyze millions of medical data, identify hidden patterns and predict diseases. One example of the successful use of artificial intelligence is the development of algorithms for diagnosing cancer from medical images, which increases the accuracy and speed of diagnosis.

2. Genomic medicine

Thanks to modern technologies, it has become easier and more convenient to determine the sequence of the human genome. This opens up new possibilities for individualized medicine, predicting the risk of development of genetically determined diseases and making it possible to develop personalized treatment approaches.

3. Telemedicine and mobile applications

The rise of smartphones and internet connectivity has led to a boom in telemedicine and mobile health applications. Patients can receive medical advice without leaving their homes and doctors can constantly monitor their condition. This is especially true during the COVID-19 pandemic.

4. Robotic surgery

Robotic surgery systems allow surgeons to perform more precise and minimally invasive surgeries. This reduces the risk of complications and speeds up the patient's recovery.

5. Nanotechnology in medicine

Nanotechnology opens up new opportunities in drug delivery, diagnostics, and body monitoring. For example, robots can deliver drugs to specific areas of the body, minimizing side effects.

6. Gene and cell therapy

Gene and cell therapy treats genetic diseases and cancers by modifying genes or using therapeutic cells. This opens up new opportunities for the treatment of previously untreatable diseases.

7. 3D printing in medicine

3D printing enables the creation of customized implants, prostheses and organ models for surgical planning. This improves surgical results and shortens rehabilitation time.

8. Information security and data protection

As the volume of healthcare data grows, it becomes increasingly important to ensure that it is secure and protected from cyber-attacks. Cybersecurity innovation is becoming an integral part of medical practice.

In short, modern medical technologies are becoming an integral part of medicine. With their help, currently considered dangerous and complicated operations carried out. Digital health makes it possible to improve people's health, to help them quickly and efficiently, and to solve the problems facing medicine.

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